

Ultrasonic velocity and related acoustical parameters of 2-(2,4-dinitrophenoxy)-1-[2-(2,4-dinitrophenoxy)naphthalene-1-yl]naphthalene solutions at 35 °C

Pooja P. Adroja, S. P. Gami, J. P. Patel and P. H. Parsania*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005, Gujarat, India

E-mail : phparsania22@gmail.com, phparsania@aol.com

Manuscript received 6 August 2009, revised 20 November 2009, accepted 26 November 2009

Abstract : The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) (2 MHz) of chloroform, THF and 2-(2,4-dinitrophenoxy)-1-[2-(2,4-dinitrophenoxy)naphthalene-1-yl]naphthalene (DBNN) solutions have been determined at 35 °C. Various acoustical parameters namely specific acoustical impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), Van der Waals constant (b), intermolecular path length (L_f), internal pressure (π), free volume (V_f), Rao's molar sound function (R), relaxation time (τ) and classical absorption coefficient ($(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$) and solvation number (S_n) have been derived from ρ , η and U data and correlated with concentration (C). A fairly good to excellent correlation has been observed between a particular parameter and C . Linear increase of Z , R , b , V_f (except chloroform), $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ and τ ; and linear decrease of κ_s , π and L_f with C supported presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions, which are further supported by nonlinear increase of S_n with C . A fairly constant Gibb's free energy of activation has been observed in both the systems.

Keywords : Ultrasonic velocity, acoustical parameters, solvation number, Gibb's free energy of activation.

Introduction

Ultrasonic velocity is highly sensitive to molecular interactions and therefore it is most widely employed in understanding nature and strength of molecular interactions¹. Ultrasonic velocity is fundamentally associated with binding forces between atoms and molecules². Variation of ultrasonic velocity and associated acoustical parameters throw light upon the structural changes due to weakly and strongly interacting components of the solutions³.

Novel materials with controlled stereochemistry have found numerous applications. 2,2'-Substituted-1,1'-binaphthyl systems have been found extensively useful in

controlling many asymmetric processes because of their stable conformation⁴. BINOL often serves as the starting material for obtaining chiral binaphthyl compounds. The 2,2'-hydroxyl groups can easily be converted into other auxiliary used in host guest chemistry for its high chiral recognition properties and its asymmetric synthesis⁵. BINOL and its derivatives have been widely used in asymmetric catalysis⁶.

In the present work an effort has been made to understand molecular interactions in 2-(2,4-dinitrophenoxy)-1-[2-(2,4-dinitrophenoxy)naphthalene-1-yl]naphthalene at 35 °C.

2-(2,4-Dinitrophenoxy)-1-[2-(2,4-dinitrophenoxy)naphthalene-1-yl]naphthalene (DBNN)

Experimental

Solvents used in the present study were purified prior to their use⁷. 1,1'-Bi-2-naphthol (DBN) was synthesized by free radical coupling reaction of 0.05 mol 2-naphthol (in 300 ml water) using FeCl₃ (14 g in 30 ml water) as a catalyst at 60 °C for 15–20 min. DBN was crystallized at least three times from toluene and methanol-water systems (yield 55.9% and m.p. 218 °C). DBNN was synthesized by condensing 0.01 mol DBN and 0.02 mol 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene using 0.02 mol 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene using 0.02 mol K₂CO₃ as a catalyst at 160 °C for 15 h. DBNN was crystallized at least three times from acetone (yield 20% and m.p. 260 °C). Stock solutions of DBNN (0.2 mol/L) were prepared in chloroform and THF. From stock solutions, a series of solutions were prepared. The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) measurements of pure solvents and solutions were carried out at 35 °C using specific gravity bottle, Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and Mittal Enterprise Interferometer (New Delhi, Model No. F-81) operating at 2 MHz, respectively. The ρ , η and U measurements were accurate to ± 0.0001 g cm⁻³, ± 0.01 m.Pas and to $\pm 0.15\%$, respectively.

Results and discussion

Experimental ρ , η and U data of pure solvents and DBNN solutions at 35 °C are reported in Table 1, from which it is observed that ρ is varied little (decreased in

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) data of DBNN at 35 °C

Concn. (%)	CHCl ₃			THF		
	ρ (kg/m ³)	η (m.Pas)	U (m s ⁻¹)	ρ (kg/m ³)	η (m.Pas)	U (m s ⁻¹)
1.545	1466.1	0.552	955.2	879.8	0.453	1233.6
3.09	1465.8	0.585	957.6	886.7	0.479	1237.6
6.18	1464.8	0.616	970	896.3	0.505	1243.2
9.27	1462.3	0.677	982.8	908	0.551	1247.2
12.36	1461.6	0.741	993.2	918.8	0.577	1259.2

chloroform and increased in THF) with concentration (C), but η and U increased considerably with C . Linear variation of ρ , η and U with C supported the presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Variation in U and ρ with C is not as appreciable as η because molecular motion is much more affected by solvent-sol-

ute interactions⁸. The least square equations and regression coefficients (R^2) are reported in Table 2 from which it is clear that a good to excellent correlation is observed in case of above mentioned parameters.

Various acoustical parameters namely specific acoustical impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), Rao's molar sound function (R), Van der Waals constant (b), intermolecular free path length (L_f), internal pressure (π), free volume (V_f), relaxation time (τ), classical absorption coefficient $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ and solvation number (S_n) were derived using ρ , η and U data according to our recent publications⁹:

Specific acoustical impedance :

$$Z = U\rho \quad (1)$$

Isentropic compressibility :

$$\kappa_s = \frac{1}{U^2\rho} \quad (2)$$

Rao's molar sound function :

$$R = \frac{M}{\rho} U^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

where M is the apparent molecular weight of the solution and can be calculated according to eq. (4) :

$$M = M_1W_1 + M_2W_2 \quad (4)$$

where W_1 and W_2 are weight fractions of solvent and solute, respectively; M_1 and M_2 are molecular weights of solvent and solute, respectively.

Van der Waals constant :

$$b = \frac{M}{\rho} \left[1 - \left[\frac{RT}{MU^2} \right] \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{MU^2}{3RT}} - 1 \right] \right] \quad (5)$$

where R is the gas constant and T is the temperature.

Internal pressure :

$$\pi = b' RT \left(\frac{K\eta}{U} \right)^{1/2} \frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M^{7/6}} \quad (6)$$

where R is the gas constant and b' (2) is the packing factor and K (4.28×10^9) is a constant. π depends on temperature, density, sound velocity and specific heat at constant pressure.

Table 2. Least square equations and regression coefficients for DBNN at 35 °C

Parameter	Least square equation and regression coefficient, R^2	
	CHCl ₃	THF
ρ (kg/m ³)	-1.25C + 1467 $R^2 = 0.926$	9.93C + 868.1 $R^2 = 0.991$
η (m.Pas)	0.047C + 0.493 $R^2 = 0.971$	0.032C + 0.417 $R^2 = 0.988$
U (m s ⁻¹)	10.12C + 941.4 $R^2 = 0.966$	6.08C + 1225 $R^2 = 0.945$
$Z \times 10^{-6}$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.013C + 1.381 $R^2 = 0.965$	0.017C + 1.063 $R^2 = 0.985$
$\kappa_s \times 10^{-10}$ (Pas)	-0.143C + 7.669 $R^2 = 0.969$	-0.149C + 7.646 $R^2 = 0.983$
$R \times 10^4$ (m ^{10/3} s ^{-1/3} mol ⁻¹)	0.423C + 7.709 $R^2 = 0.985$	1.07C + 8.194 $R^2 = 0.990$
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-0.068C + 3.822 $R^2 = 0.934$	-0.264C + 3.893 $R^2 = 0.987$
$b \times 10^{-5}$ (m ³)	0.392C + 7.746 $R^2 = 0.987$	0.968C + 7.538 $R^2 = 0.990$
$L_f \times 10^{-11}$ (m)	-0.056C + 5.800 $R^2 = 0.968$	-0.058C + 5.792 $R^2 = 0.982$
$V_f \times 10^7$ (m ³)	-0.1C + 3.597 $R^2 = 0.874$	0.272C + 3.135 $R^2 = 0.965$
$(\alpha/f^2)_{cl} \times 10^{-14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)	0.053C + 1.076 $R^2 = 0.961$	0.028C + 0.692 $R^2 = 0.956$
$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	0.328C + 5.114 $R^2 = 0.968$	0.203C + 4.299 $R^2 = 0.972$
S_n	-0.106C ² + 0.992C + 0.518 $R^2 = 0.963$	-0.368C ³ + 3.518C ² - 10.15C + 17.34 $R^2 = 0.970$

Free volume :

$$V_f = \left[\frac{MU}{K\eta} \right]^{3/2} \quad (7)$$

where $K = (4.28 \times 10^9)$ is constant.

Intermolecular free path length :

$$L_f = K (\kappa_s)^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

where $K = (93.875 + 0.375T) \times 10^{-8}$ is a temperature dependent constant.

Classical absorption coefficient :

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2} \right)_{cl} = \frac{8\pi^2 \eta}{3U^3 \rho} \quad (9)$$

Classical absorption coefficient has its origin in the viscosity of the medium.

Viscous relaxation time :

The resistance offered by viscous force in the flow of sound wave appears as a classical absorption associated with viscous relaxation time :

$$\tau = \frac{4\eta}{3\rho U^2} \quad (10)$$

Solvation number :

$$S_n = \frac{M_2}{M_1 \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_s}{\kappa_{s_1}} \right) \left(\frac{100 - X}{X} \right)} \quad (11)$$

where X is the number of grams of solute in 100 g of the solution.

The parameters are correlated with C and the least square equations along with regression coefficients are

reported in Table 2. A fairly good to excellent correlation is observed between a given parameter and C ; whenever nonlinear behavior is observed polynomial regression is performed.

Z , R , b , $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$, and τ increased linearly with C , while κ_s , π and L_f decreased linearly with C , V_f decreased in chloroform, while it increased with C in THF. Linear increase or decrease of the said parameters further confirmed the presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Variation of U in the solution depends on intermolecular free path length⁸. When ultrasonic waves are incident on the solution, the molecules get perturbed. Since the medium has some elasticity and hence perturbed molecules regain their equilibrium positions. When a solute is added to a solvent, its molecules attract certain solvent molecules towards them. This phenomenon is known as compression. Every solvent has a limit for compression and is known as limiting compressibility. Generally κ_s decreases with C . The decrease of κ_s may be due to the aggregation of solvent molecules around solute molecules supporting strong solvent-solute interactions.

According to Jacobson's intermolecular free length theory for liquids, the molecules of the liquid are assumed to be spherical and the average value of the distance that the ultrasonic waves travel between the two molecules is called the intermolecular free path length. Decrease of L_f with C further supported solvent-solute interactions. Due to solvent-solute interactions, structural arrangement is considerably changed.

The dispersion of U in the system gives information about the characteristic time of the relaxation process that causes the dispersion.

According to Eyring rate process theory¹⁰, variation of τ with temperature (T) can be given by

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{kT}{h} e^{-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}}$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant, h is the Planck's constant, R is the gas constant, T is the temperature and ΔG^* is the Gibb's free energy of activation. Observed τ is due to structural relaxation processes. Rearrangement of the molecules is a cooperative process involving the movement of many molecules around a hole in the system¹¹. According to above equation, the value of ΔG^* was cal-

culated at different concentrations (Table 3). A fairly constant values of ΔG^* in chloroform (3.49 kJ mol⁻¹) and in THF (2.94 kJ mol⁻¹) indicates that the condensation in the phase and absorption due to rearrangement of molecules are independent of C and are characteristic physical properties of the solute only.

Table 3. Gibb's free energy of activation for DBNN in chloroform and THF

Concen. (%)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
	Chloroform	THF
1.545	3.23	2.72
3.09	3.37	2.83
6.18	3.44	2.91
9.27	3.62	3.10
12.36	3.79	3.13

Depending on the nature of the solvent and solute molecular interactions may either lead to contraction or expansion. Internal pressure of a solution is sensitive to molecular interactions namely solvent-solute interactions, quantum mechanical dispersion forces and dielectric forces, which play an important role in transport properties of the solutions. Decrease of π with C suggested decrease of cohesive forces and vice versa. Presence of molecular interactions in solutions is further supported by nonlinear increase of solvation number (S_n) (Fig. 1). Molecular interactions are influenced by the nature and structure, pressure, concentration, nature of the substituent, etc.

Fig. 1. The plots of S_n against C for DBNN at 35 °C.

The presence of polar substituents in the solute molecules lead to enhanced molecular interactions. Solvation causes compressibility of the molecules. Thus solvation is a measure of structure forming or breaking tendency of the solutes. The dipole-dipole interactions of the opposite type

favor the structure formation; while of the same type disrupt the structure formed previously. In the present case positive values of S_n indicated predominant dipole-dipole interactions of the opposite type. In conclusion, derived acoustical parameters suggested the presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. DBNN possesses structure forming tendency in both the solvent systems.

Acknowledgement

Authors (SPG and JPP) are thankful to UGC-SAP Grant (UGC Grant No. UGC (SAP)/6/DRS/2004, 1.4.2004) for financial help for MSc dissertation.

References

- (i) J. F. Kincaid and H. Eyring, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, **5**, 587; (ii) S. K. Mehta and R. K. Chauhan, *J. Sol. Chem.*, 1996, **26**, 295; (iii) R. K. Wadi and R. K. Goyal, *J. Sol. Chem.*, 1992, **21**, 163; (iv) R. K. Dewan, S. K. Mehta, R. Parashar and K. Bala, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1991, **87**, 1561.
- (i) V. A. Tabhane, *Acoust. Lett.*, 1983, **6**, 120; (ii) Isht Vibhu, Amit Mishra, Manisha Gupta and J. P. Shukla, *Indian Acad. Sci.*, 2004, **62**, 1147.
- J. D. Pandey and A. K. Shukla, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.*, 1997, **15**, 37.
- L. Pu, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 2405.
- Y. Naruta, F. Tani, N. Ishihara and K. Murayama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 6865.
- (i) S. Y. Tosaki, R. Tsuji, T. Oshima and M. Shibasaki, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 2147; (ii) Y. Tian, Q. C. Yang, T. C. W. Mark and K. S. Chan, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 3951; (iii) S. Y. Tosaki, Y. Horiuchi, T. Nemoto, T. Oshima and M. Shibasaki, *Chemistry a Europ. J.*, 2004, **10**, 1527; (iv) A. Sekine, T. Oshima and M. Shibasaki, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 75.
- "Vogel's Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", 5th ed., ELBS, London, 395.
- (i) W. Bell and R. A. Pethrick, *Polymer*, 1982, **23**, 369; (ii) B. Jacobson, *Acta Chem. Scand. (Denmark)*, 1952, **6**, 1485.
- (i) D. D. Madhvi, F. D. Karia and P. H. Parsania, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 588; (ii) B. J. Gangani and P. H. Parsania, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.*, 2008, **30**, 90.
- L. E. Kinsler and A. R. Frey, "Fundamentals of Acoustus", Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi, 1978, 224.
- N. Hiral and H. Eyring, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 1959, **29**, 810.

